

Deliverable D7.1 Establish minimal shared interoperability metadata

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

BAO	Bioassay Ontology
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BIA	BioImage Archive
Bioschemas	Bioschemas community profiles for life-sciences metadata
CL	Cell Ontology
CLO	Cell Line Ontology
CMPO	Cellular Microscopy Phenotype Ontology
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DOID	Human Disease Ontology
DwC	Darwin Core
EFO	Experimental Factor Ontology
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FBbi	Biological Imaging Methods Ontology
GO	Gene Ontology
HPO	Human Phenotype Ontology
IDR	Image Data Resource
INSDC	International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration
IRI	Internationalized Resource Identifier
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data
LinkML	Linked Data Modeling Language
MI	PSI Molecular Interactions Controlled Vocabulary
MONDO	Mondo Disease Ontology
NCBITaxon	NCBI organismal classification (NCBI Taxonomy)
NGFF	Next-generation file format

OBO	Open Biological and Biomedical Ontologies
OME	Open Microscopy Environment
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
PIDInst	Persistent Identification of Instruments
RDF	Resource Description Framework
REMBI	Recommended Metadata for Biological Images
RO-Crate	Research Object Crate
ROR	Research Organization Registry
SHACL	Shapes Constraint Language
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
SSBD	A platform for Systems Science of Biological Dynamics
UBERON	Uberon Multi-species Anatomy Ontology
UO	Units of Measurement Ontology
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WP	Work Package
wwPDB	worldwide Protein Data Bank

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Executive Summary

Work Package 7 of foundingGIDE was designed to establish a core, shared set of metadata sufficient to enable cross-resource discovery and search across the participating bioimaging data resources (BioImage Archive (BIA), Image Data Resource (IDR) and SSBD) without requiring those resources to adopt a single shared schema. This deliverable describes the resulting specification: the foundingGIDE search input RO-Crate profile (v0.2, January 2026), which defines a minimal interoperability metadata set as a profile of the RO-Crate community standard, together with a companion JSON-LD context that defines profile's terms in schema.org, Bioschemas, Darwin Core and OBO Foundry vocabularies. The profile is built directly on the twelve commonly-held metadata components identified in Deliverable D6.1, and adopts a two-tier structure: a small core of mandatory fields that drives cross-resource search, and an extended REMBI-aligned layer that supports richer expression for resource-specific metadata..

The approach is now in operational use: all of the GIDE bioimaging resources have implemented profile-conformant exporters, the shared catalogue snapshot is the subject of Deliverable D10.1, and the resulting cross-resource search portal and API are documented in Deliverable D11.1. This document presents the rationale for the choice of approach, the structure and semantics of the profile, and three worked examples drawn from BIA, IDR and SSBD.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background and motivation

Bioimaging data management at scale is less mature than other life sciences data domains. Nucleotide sequence data and protein structure data have for decades been shared and integrated through global consortia such as the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC; Karsch-Mizrachi et al., 2012) and the worldwide Protein Data Bank (wwPDB; Berman et al., 2003), in both cases by means of common metadata schemas and standardised annotations that make data findable and computable across institutions. Bioimaging has long aspired to comparable interoperability (Swedlow et al., 2021), but has historically lacked an equivalent agreement on metadata: imaging instruments, modalities and analytical pipelines vary widely, the volumes of data produced are now routinely on the scale of terabytes per study, and 3 of the major resources, BIA (Hartley et al., 2022), IDR (Williams et al., 2017) and SSBD:database (Kyoda et al., 2025), have each developed internal metadata models tailored to their host communities and operational constraints.

Deliverable D6.1 of foundingGIDE compared these three models in detail and reached two conclusions that frame the present work. First, a substantial common core does exist in practice: twelve metadata components (study identifier, authors, publication, license, release date, imaging method, organism, channel content, channel biological entity, data identifier, dimension, and pixel/voxel size) are held in common across BIA, IDR and SSBD. Second, the only ontologies adopted universally are NCBI Taxonomy for species and the Biological Imaging Methods Ontology (FBbi) for imaging methods; elsewhere, resources have made locally reasonable but divergent choices, for example PubChem for chemical compounds at IDR versus ChEBI at SSBD. D6.1 recommended a phased approach: standardise the shared components first, address vocabulary divergences next, and only then address resource-specific extensions.

Given the impracticality of centralising bioimaging data at the scale at which it is now produced, the harmonisation that foundingGIDE needs at this point in time is metadata-interchange level rather than a single schema shared across all resources. What is required is a contract that allows independently-operated resources to expose comparable information through compatible interfaces, while leaving their internal models intact. This deliverable defines that contract.

1.2 Purpose and scope of this deliverable

This deliverable is the specification component for Work Package 7 of foundingGIDE, which is concerned with establishing the shared 'core' metadata subset that allows cross-comparison across the SSBD and BioImage Archive/REMBI models. It defines the foundingGIDE search input RO-Crate profile, a metadata specification expressed as a profile of the RO-Crate community standard (RO-Crate 1.2), together with the JSON-LD context that grounds its terms. The profile is published at <https://www.gide-project.org/ro-crate/search/1.0/profile> and maintained openly in <https://github.com/foundingGIDE/gide-search>.

The scope of this deliverable is deliberately narrow. We describe the rationale for the choice of approach, the structure and semantics of the profile, three worked examples from BIA, IDR and SSBD, and the route to a stable v1.0. We do not attempt to redevelop the internal metadata models of the participating resources: this is explicitly outside the WP7 brief and would not, in any case, be tractable in the timescale of foundingGIDE. We do not address image-level metadata: the profile is study-level by design, and image-level metadata is treated as the responsibility of the file-embedded

layer based on OME-NGFF, in line with the hybrid approach proposed in D6.1 §4.3. We do not address preclinical metadata, which is the subject of a parallel work package (D8.1). And we do not document the harvested data snapshot itself, the SHACL validation pipeline, or the resulting cross-resource search portal: these are the subjects of Deliverables D10.1 and D11.1 respectively.

1.3 Position in foundingGIDE

D7.1 sits at the centre of a chain of foundingGIDE deliverables. It consumes the outputs of D6.1 and D5.1 and provides the contract against which subsequent work in WP10 and WP11 is built. The dependencies are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1: Dependencies between D7.1 and other foundingGIDE deliverables.

Deliverable	Work Package	Role with respect to D7.1
D6.1 — Report in metadata model overlap and gaps	WP6	Input. Provided the comparative analysis of BIA/IDR/SSBD metadata models and the identification of the twelve commonly-held components on which this profile is built.
D2.1 — Landscape analysis of existing ontologies and recommendations on a set of imaging ontologies	WP2	Input. Provides the ontology selections (NCBI Taxonomy, FBbi, and others) that are referenced as DefinedTerm and Taxon @id values in profile-conformant crates.
D7.1 (this deliverable)	WP7	Defines the profile.
D10.1 — Model description and snapshot	WP10	Applied data. Implements profile-conformant export pipelines for the three target resources, validates the harvested crates against a SHACL representation of the profile, and publishes the joint snapshot.
D11.1 — Data portal and supporting API	WP11	Applied use. Ingests the harvested snapshot to power the cross-resource search portal and API.
D8.1 — Recommended harmonised metadata model for preclinical image datasets	WP8	Sibling. Addresses the preclinical domain; possible future alignment.

2. Choice of data modelling approach

2.1 Requirements derived from D6.1

D6.1 made clear, by way of an extended comparative analysis of BIA, IDR and SSBD, that any approach to shared metadata in foundingGIDE would need to satisfy a particular set of constraints. We extract these here as design requirements for the modelling approach.

Table 2: Mapping requirements to implementation plan.

Requirement	Basis in D6.1	Consequence for D7.1
Accommodate graph-shaped data	Conceptually equivalent metadata can occur at different positions in different resources; for example, organism information is attached at study level in IDR but at study-component level in BIA and SSBD.	Use a graph-based representation rather than a flat record schema, so comparable concepts can be linked and queried independently of their position in a local hierarchy.
Represent ontology terms as resolvable identifiers	D6.1 found heterogeneous ontology use across resources, with NCBI Taxonomy and FBbi the only universally adopted ontologies.	Represent species, imaging methods and related terms as IRIs rather than opaque strings, enabling direct cross-resource matching and later vocabulary mapping.
Provide a portable, self-describing exchange unit	WP10 requires catalogue export, harvesting and snapshotting across independently operated resources.	Use a single metadata document per study that carries the information needed for harvesting, validation and indexing.
Allow resource-specific extension	BIA, IDR and SSBD each hold additional metadata reflecting their scientific scope, curation practices and operational models.	Define a minimum shared contract while allowing each resource to include richer or resource-specific metadata where available.

Support flexible, open-world validation	The federation should validate shared requirements without treating additional local metadata as an error.	Use a validation approach that checks required fields and cardinalities while permitting extra properties and entities.
Build on a recognised community standard	A locally invented model would create a long-term maintenance and tooling burden for foundingGIDE.	Prefer an actively maintained standard with existing tooling, community governance and alignment with neighbouring research-data metadata frameworks.

These six requirements together rule out a number of otherwise reasonable approaches and point toward a particular family of solutions built on linked-data and JSON-LD foundations.

2.2 Aligning to the RO-Crate standard

RO-Crate is a community standard for packaging research data and its associated metadata in a structured form, built on JSON-LD and grounded primarily in schema.org. It satisfies every requirement in §2.1, and brings several additional properties that prove useful in the foundingGIDE context.

JSON-LD with schema.org grounding. RO-Crate uses JSON-LD as its serialisation format, which makes every conformant document simultaneously valid JSON (consumable by any general-purpose tooling) and a true RDF graph. The default vocabulary is schema.org, supplemented by community-defined extensions where needed. This dual character is important in practice: reusers who are familiar with JSON can work with the format directly, while semantic-web practitioners can load it into their own infrastructure with no conversion step. Within the project we apply both of these approaches, the search indexing pipeline uses JSON, the SHACL validation uses the graph.

Detached RO-Crates for federated metadata exchange. Version 1.2 of the RO-Crate specification introduced the detached RO-Crate construct, in which the `ro-crate-metadata.json` file stands alone with no associated payload. The construct is purpose-built for the case in which metadata is exchanged but data remains at its publishing resource (the bioimaging case). Each resource exports its catalogue as a set of detached RO-Crates, one per study; downstream consumers can build a shared index or shared graph.

Profiles as the constraint mechanism. RO-Crate 1.2 also formalised the notion of a profile: a layered specification that defines additional structural constraints on top of the base RO-Crate. A profile is the right level at which to express what foundingGIDE needs: not a new schema, not a new format, but an agreement among participating resources about which fields will be present, what semantics

they will carry, and which vocabularies will be drawn on. The profile mechanism also aligns naturally with the REMBI modularity argument articulated in D6.1 §4.1, in which a shared core can be defined without forcing convergence on a monolithic schema.

Maturity and ecosystem. RO-Crate is an actively maintained community standard with stable tooling in multiple programming languages, a published specification process, and adoption across a range of research infrastructures and projects.

2.3 LinkML evaluation

We evaluated LinkML against the requirements in §2.1 during the early phase of WP7 and found it to be a strong candidate in several respects: it is well-documented, has active community support, and the tooling has a low technical bar for entry for schema authoring and validation.

However, we ultimately did not adopt LinkML for this deliverable. Currently, LinkML's validation is closed-world by default: a model declares what is permitted and a validator flags anything not declared as a violation. This is appropriate for many use cases, but it works against the open-extensibility requirement in §2.1. In a federation in which BIA, IDR and SSBD each have substantial resource-specific metadata that should not be lost during export, a validator that treats unmodelled fields as errors imposes a continuous coordination burden on schema maintenance. We needed a validation regime that could enforce the core contract while permitting each resource to extend its exports with its own information at will. A parallel effort to improve support for what are known as extra slots in LinkML has been progressing through the LinkML community but has not yet been released for all implementations. This effort was supported by members of FoundingGIDE for the possible future integration of LinkML into joint validation systems.

While LinkML's tooling can work with JSON-LD, it makes strong and restrictive assumptions about the mapping between the structure of the serialised json and its respective rdf graph. For a generic JSON-LD document, it is therefore often not possible to write a single LinkML schema to validate both the graph and the json: two parallel schemas would have to be maintained, leading to increased maintenance costs and risks of divergence. The RO-Crate standard uses a structure that is not aligned to the assumptions made in the existing LinkML tooling. This is an issue that we have not yet addressed.

2.4 Prior art: the 2024 OME-NGFF Challenge

The approach taken here was not invented from scratch for foundingGIDE. The 2024 OME-NGFF Challenge, a community-wide effort to produce a large-scale, FAIR snapshot of bioimaging data in the OME-Zarr format, used a preliminary RO-Crate profile as the metadata layer for its outputs (<https://github.com/ome/ome2024-ngff-challenge/>). The Challenge presented approximately 500 TB of OME-Zarr data and demonstrated the use of two specific identifier vocabularies (FBbi for imaging methods and NCBI Taxonomy for species) as the controlled vocabularies that the bioimaging community is most prepared to act on consistently.

2.5 End-to-end metadata exchange

The decisions described above combine into an end-to-end flow. Figure 1 illustrates the path from each resource's internal metadata to the cross-resource search portal.

Figure 1. Flow of metadata documents through to indexing system and search portal

Each resource implements an export pipeline that emits detached RO-Crates conformant with the profile, one per study. The crates use the shared JSON-LD context to ensure that term IRIs resolve identically across resources, and they reference ontology terms (in particular, NCBI Taxonomy entries for species and FBbi terms for imaging methods) as resolvable URIs rather than as opaque strings.

The strength of this flow is that it asks little of the participating resources beyond the export pipeline itself. There is no convergence on a shared internal schema, no shared operational database, no joint runtime dependency between resources. This enables easier onboarding of future data resources.

3. The foundingGIDE search RO-Crate profile

The profile is published at <https://www.gide-project.org/ro-crate/search/1.0/profile> and the human-readable specification and JSON-LD context are maintained in <https://github.com/foundingGIDE/gide-search>.

3.1 Design principles

The profile is built on design principles which follow from the analysis in Section 2.

Detached RO-Crate as the unit of exchange. A conformant document is a single `ro-crate-metadata.json` file with no associated payload.

Resolvable root identifier. The root Dataset entity carries an `@id` that is the absolute URL of the entry in its publishing resource. This preserves provenance, supports portal back-links, and gives every entity in the joint graph a stable, dereferenceable anchor.

Two tiers: a small core and an extended layer. The profile distinguishes between a minimum contract that every conformant crate must satisfy (§3.3) and an extended layer of strongly-recommended and optional entities that resources may use to expose richer detail where they have it (§3.4).

Open schema. Beyond the minimum contract, the profile imposes no closed-set constraint on which additional properties or entities a crate may contain. Resources are free to extend their exports with their own information; harvesters and validators treat such additions as benign.

3.2 Mapping D6.1's twelve components onto the profile

D6.1 §2.1 identified twelve metadata components that are held in common across the three target resources. The profile captures each of these where it can be expressed at the study level. Table 3 sets out the mapping in full.

Table 3: Mapping of D6.1's twelve universally-shared metadata components onto the foundingGIDE profile.

D6.1 component	Hierarchy in D6.1	Profile field	Vocabulary	Tier
Study identifier	Study	Dataset @id (resolvable URL) and Dataset identifier	—	Core (MUST)
Authors	Study	Dataset author → Person and/or Organisation	ORCID for Person @id; ROR for Organisation @id	Core (MUST)
Publication	Study	Dataset seeAlso → ScholarlyArticle	DOI preferred for @id	Extended (optional)
License	Study	Dataset license	URL to a licence description	Core (MUST)
Release date	Study	Dataset datePublished	ISO 8601	Core (MUST)
Imaging method	Study Component	Dataset measurementMethod → DefinedTerm and/or LabProtocol	FBbi for the DefinedTerm @id (SHOULD)	Core (MUST exist; SHOULD use FBbi)
Organism	varies (Study at IDR; Study)	Dataset about → Taxon (and/or BioSample)	NCBI Taxonomy for the Taxon @id (SHOULD)	Core (MUST exist; SHOULD use NCBITaxon)

D6.1 component	Hierarchy in D6.1	Profile field	Vocabulary	Tier
	Component at (BIA, SSBD)	<i>taxonomicRange</i> → <i>Taxon</i>)		
Channel — content	Image data	<i>Not captured at study level</i>	—	Not in scope for study level exchange
Channel — biological entity	Image data	<i>Not captured at study level</i>	—	Not in scope for study level exchange
Data identifier (image-level)	Image data	<i>Not captured at study level</i>	—	Not in scope for study level exchange
Dimension	Image data	<i>Not captured at study level</i>	—	Not in scope for study level exchange
Pixel/voxel size	Image data	<i>Not captured at study level</i>	—	Not in scope for study level exchange

Seven of the twelve components are study-level concepts and are captured directly by the profile. Five are image-level and explicitly not in scope for this level of metadata exchange.

In addition to the seven D6.1 components captured directly, the profile carries several entities and properties that go beyond D6.1's minimum-twelve set but are motivated by the use cases identified in D6.1 §3.1 and by the practical requirements of a cross-resource search portal. These include the dataset's name, description, keywords, thumbnailUrl, and publisher; richer descriptions of biological samples through BioSample; richer descriptions of imaging methods through LabProtocol; funding attribution through Grant; and dataset extent through QuantitativeValue (file count and bytes).

3.3 The core (mandatory) layer

Every conformant detached RO-Crate must contain the following structure.

The self-describing RO-Crate Metadata Descriptor. A single entity with @id ro-crate-metadata.json, @type CreativeWork, declaring conformsTo <https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.2> and linking via about to the root Dataset.

A root Dataset. A single entity of @type Dataset, linked from the metadata descriptor's about property. The root Dataset must carry the following properties:

- **@id** — the absolute URL of the entry at its publishing resource.
- **name** — a human-readable name for the study.
- **description** — an overview of the study, providing the context in which it is meaningful.
- **datePublished** — a single string value in ISO 8601 date format.
- **license** — a URL to a licence description.
- **author** — one or more entities of **@type Person** (preferred; with an ORCID **@id** where available) or **Organisation** (with a ROR **@id** where available).
- **publisher** — a single entity of **@type Organisation** representing the resource that publishes the entry at the URL given as the **Dataset's @id**.
- **about** — one or more entities describing the biological subject of the study. At least one must be present. If it is of **@type Taxon** **taxon**, it SHOULD use an NCBI Taxonomy IRIR as its **@id**.
- **measurementMethod** — one or more entities describing the imaging method or methods used. At least one must be present and if it is of **@type DefinedTerm**, it SHOULD use an FBbi IRI as its **@id**.

This minimum is sufficient to drive cross-resource search of the kind described in D11.1: every conformant crate contains a study identifier, attribution metadata, a licence and date, a publisher, a typed organism, and a typed imaging method. The use of NCBI Taxonomy and FBbi as the recommended vocabularies for the two core ontology fields means that organism-based and method-based search can be implemented as IRI-equality queries against the joint graph, rather than as string matching.

3.4 The extended (REMBI-aligned) layer

Beyond the core, the profile defines a strongly-recommended layer of additional entities and properties that allow conformant crates to expose richer detail where the publishing resource has it. The structure of this layer follows REMBI (Sarkans et al., 2021), of which the foundingGIDE profile can be regarded as a concrete implementation in RO-Crate form.

BioSample. Entities of **@type BioSample** (Bioschemas BioSample 0.2-DRAFT) may be attached to the root **Dataset** via **about** to describe the biological samples imaged in the study. A **BioSample** carries a **name**, a **description**, an optional **taxonomicRange** pointing to one or more **Taxon** entities, and an optional **hasCellLine** property (BAO BAO_0002004) pointing to a **DefinedTerm** representing the cell line. The same **Taxon** referenced from a **BioSample's taxonomicRange** must also be explicitly attached to the root **Dataset's about**, to ensure that organism queries against the root entity remain consistent across resources.

LabProtocol. Entities of **@type LabProtocol** (Bioschemas LabProtocol 0.8-DRAFT) may be attached to the root **Dataset** via **measurementMethod** to describe the imaging procedures used. A **LabProtocol** carries a **name**, a **description**, an optional **labEquipment** description, and an optional **measurementTechnique** pointing to one or more **DefinedTerm** entities. The **measurementTechnique DefinedTerm** SHOULD use an FBbi IRI as its **@id**. As with **BioSample**, any **DefinedTerm** referenced

from a [LabProtocol](#)'s [measurementTechnique](#) must also be explicitly attached to the root [Dataset](#)'s [measurementMethod](#).

ScholarlyArticle, Grant, QuantitativeValue. A [Dataset](#) may carry an optional [seeAlso](#) property pointing to one or more [ScholarlyArticle](#) entities (with DOI [@id](#) where available), a [funder](#) property pointing to one or more [Grant](#) entities, and a [size](#) property pointing to one or more [QuantitativeValue](#) entities. Two [QuantitativeValue](#) entries are recommended in particular: the total file count (with [unitCode](#) http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UO_0000189 and [unitText](#) "file count") and the total dataset size in bytes (with [unitCode](#) http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UO_0000233 and [unitText](#) "bytes"). These two figures give the portal and downstream consumers a useful estimate of dataset extent without requiring any data transfer.

Descriptive properties. A [Dataset](#) may also carry [thumbnailUrl](#) (one or more URLs pointing to example images, used by the portal for visual presentation), [keywords](#) (free-text tags), and [identifier](#) (the unique identifier used internally by the publishing resource, distinct from the resolvable [@id](#)).

Other ontologies welcome. The profile is open: the absence of a particular property from this section does not preclude a resource from including it. SSBD, for example, attaches Gene Ontology terms ([DefinedTerm](#) entities with [obo:GO_*](#) IRIs) directly to the root [Dataset](#)'s [about](#) to indicate functional biological context. This is permitted, and is consumed by the joint graph as additional RDF triples; it is not required of other resources, and validators do not treat its presence as a violation.

3.5 The JSON-LD context

The profile's terms are grounded in a published JSON-LD context, [gide-search-context.jsonld](#), which extends the base RO-Crate 1.2 context with foundingGIDE-specific vocabulary. Compliant crates load the base context first and then layer the foundingGIDE-specific context on top.

Three vocabulary families are imported beyond schema.org and RO-Crate's defaults. **Darwin Core** ([dwc:](#), [dwciri:](#)) is the established standard for biodiversity and taxonomic data; the profile draws on it for [scientificName](#), [vernacularName](#) and [measurementMethod](#) because schema.org does not provide sufficiently typed equivalents. **The Bioassay Ontology** ([bao:](#)) is used for [hasCellLine](#), because [schema.org](#) and or BioSchemas do not have a sufficiently specific property to distinguish this data from other possible links from the same entity. **The Open Biological and Biomedical Ontologies prefix** ([obo:](#)) is a convenience namespace used inline in [@id](#) values to refer to OBO Foundry terms, for example [obo:NCBITaxon_9606](#) for *Homo sapiens* or [obo:FBbi_00000251](#) for confocal microscopy. The [xsd:](#) prefix supports XML Schema datatypes where typed values are required (notably [datePublished](#)).

The Bioschemas type aliases ([BioSample](#), [LabProtocol](#), [labEquipment](#)) are imported because the corresponding upstream terms remain at draft status and have not yet resolved to canonical schema.org URIs; we use the proposed <http://schema.org/...> URIs in anticipation of their adoption.

The context is intended to be stable: terms defined in it MUST NOT be redefined to point at different IRIs by extending crates. Additional terms MAY be added by individual resources to support their own extensions.

3.6 Profile representations

The profile has two physical representations:

The human-readable specification ([gide_profile.md](#), this document and its published form at the permalink above) is the authoritative reference for design intent: it explains the rationale for each design decision, sets out the cardinalities and vocabularies expected of each field, and provides the worked examples in §3.7.

The machine-readable SHACL shape graph ([gide_profile_shacl_shape.ttl](#)) expresses the profile's structural constraints in a form suitable for automated validation. It declares the required properties of each entity class, enforces cardinality where the profile specifies it, and is used in D10.1's harvesting pipeline to check the conformance of crates exported by BIA, IDR and SSBD.

3.7 Worked examples

To illustrate the profile in operation, we present a detailed walkthrough of one exemplar crate from BIA (§3.7.1), a comparative view of one exemplar from each of the three resources (§3.7.2), and a brief discussion of what these examples demonstrate about the profile (§3.7.3). All three exemplars are profile-conformant detached RO-Crates produced by the resources themselves; the URLs of the source files are given in the references.

3.7.1 Walkthrough: BioImage Archive S-BIAD1445

This section is a detailed description of the semantics and structure of a particular RO-Crate, generated from the BioImage Archive submission S-BIAD1445. It covers the objects found in the `ro-crate-metadata.json`, their connections, and key features.

As with any `ro-crate-metadata.json`, the root of the document is a self-describing entity, with `@id "ro-crate-metadata.json"` that points to the root Dataset through the `about` property. This object provides a unified starting point for reading any RO-Crate.

The root Dataset object represents the whole dataset, and connects it to the key provenance metadata (authors, license, funding), as well as scientific metadata (protocols, descriptions of biological specimens etc). RO-Crate's guidance is to use suitable absolute identifiers where possible, and fall back to relative identifiers within the document, therefore the `@id` of the dataset is the link to the page for the dataset on the bioimage archive's website. (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/bioimages/studies/S-BIAD1445>)

Information directly attached to the root dataset includes:

- A name (Neurons and astrocytes have distinct organelle signatures and responses to stress)

- A longer description.
- The date when it was first published on the BioImage Archive website
- The license for the data (a link to the CC0 deed) which is assumed to apply to all the data in the dataset.
- The identifier used in the bioimage archive (S-BIAD1445)
- A set of keywords that summarise the dataset, useful for search (e.g. Primary neurons)

The dataset also links to other objects included in the ro-crate-metadata.json, as well as having some empty fields that are not used for this entry (citation, funder).

For authors, where available, an ORCID was used as their identifier. In order to still be readable as a standalone document, each author has a name, and email regardless of whether they have an ORCID. They link to an Organisation via the affiliation property, which uses an RORID as the identifier (and is described by name University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill). The root dataset is also linked to a publisher, the BioImage Archive, which uses the id of <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/bioimage-archive/>, which is described through the name property.

The scientific metadata is linked through two properties: about and measurementMethod. The subject of the dataset is described via the about property. It is required to have at least one subject, which can be a BioSample or a Taxon. In this case a number of BioSample (different cultures of cells) and a single biosample (*Rattus norvegicus*) are included. The BioSamples have names and descriptions, and are also connected to the Taxon, which is described with scientificName.

The techniques used to create the data are connected to the root dataset via measurementMethod, here there are three: an ontology term from FBbi, and two LabProtocol. The OntologyTerm provides a general description of the kind of imaging performed (confocal microscopy) which can be easily compared with across datasets. The other two LabProtocols provide more detailed descriptions of the technique, and the labEquipment that was used.

Finally, two quantitative measurements of the dataset are provided (QuantitativeValues), both through the size property on the root dataset. Defined through the unitText, unitCode, and value, they indicate the dataset has 2240 files, and 2329250106572 bytes (2.3TB).

3.7.2 Comparative view across resources

Table 4 summarises the equivalent structure across one exemplar from each of the three resources: BIA's S-BIAD1445 (the study described above), IDR's idr0108 (a super-resolution microscopy study of the nuclear pore complex), and SSBD's 124-Ueda-miPSRetina (an immunofluorescence study of mouse iPS-cell-derived retinal organoids).

Table 4: Comparative summary of one exemplar conformant crate from each resource.

Aspect	BIA (S-BIAD1445)	IDR (idr0108)	SSBD (124-Ueda-miPSRetina)
Authors	11 Person entities; mixed ORCID / local; ROR-identified affiliation	1 Person; ORCID; givenName / familyName split; named address	5 Person entities; no ORCIDs; RIKEN affiliation
Organism (about → Taxon)	1 Taxon: NCBITaxon:10116 (<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>)	1 Taxon: NCBITaxon:9606 (<i>Homo sapiens</i>)	1 Taxon: NCBITaxon:10090 (<i>Mus musculus</i>)
BioSamples	6 (control / arsenite / thapsigargin × neurons / astrocytes)	1	1
Other entities under about	—	—	3 Gene Ontology DefinedTerm entities (rod-cell differentiation; photoreceptor development; photoreceptor cilium)
Imaging method (measurementMethod → DefinedTerm)	FBbi:00000251 (confocal microscopy)	MI:2213 (super-resolution microscopy)	FBbi:00000265 (recorded image)
LabProtocols	2 (with labEquipment describing the Zeiss LSM 880)	5 (super-resolution; growth; treatment; image acquisition; data analysis), referencing FBbi, MI and EFO	1
Publications (seeAlso)	—	1 ScholarlyArticle (DOI)	1 ScholarlyArticle (PubMed URL)
Dataset extent (size)	2,240 files; 2.3 TB	—	62 files; 155.2 MB
Licence	CC0 1.0	CC-BY-4.0	CC-BY-4.0

3.7.3 What the worked examples demonstrate

Three observations follow from comparing the exemplars.

All three crates satisfy the core MUSTs. Each carries a resolvable root `@id`, a name and description, a date, a licence, at least one author, a publisher, at least one `Taxon` under `about`, and at least one `DefinedTerm` under `measurementMethod`. Cross-resource queries that rely only on the core layer (for example, *"return all studies of human cells using super-resolution microscopy"*) function correctly against the joint graph regardless of which resource published the entry.

The extended layer flexes naturally per resource. BIA provides rich `BioSample` variation, reflecting the experimental design of stress-response studies that compare multiple treatment conditions. IDR brings more complex `LabProtocol` chains that document growth, treatment, acquisition and analysis as a methodologically rich pipeline. SSBD attaches Gene Ontology terms directly to `about` to surface functional biological context. None of these choices breaks the profile, and each accurately reflects what the publishing resource already records internally.

The open-schema principle is observably in use. Two extensions to the published vocabulary appear in the worked examples. IDR's `idr0108` uses `MI:2213` (from the PSI Molecular Interactions Controlled Vocabulary) for its core `measurementMethod DefinedTerm` rather than an FBbi term, because the more specific super-resolution-microscopy concept it needed was not yet available in FBbi. SSBD's `124-Ueda-miPSRetina` attaches Gene Ontology terms to `about` to encode functional context that is meaningful to its user community. Both of these are permitted under the open-schema rule and are consumed by the joint graph as additional RDF triples.

3.8 Implementation evidence

All three resources have implemented profile-conformant exporters, maintained at:

- <https://github.com/BioImage-Archive/gide-ro-crate> (BIA)
- https://github.com/German-BioImaging/idr_study_crates (IDR)
- <https://github.com/openssbd/gide-ro-crate> (SSBD)

The joint RDF graph supports SPARQL federation across the harvested crates, with example queries returning consistent cross-resource results (D10.1 Figure 2D and Table 1).

The cross-resource search portal described in D11.1 is built on top of the harvested snapshot and demonstrates end-to-end utility of the profile in driving real user-facing search.

Taken together, these implementations show that the profile defined in this deliverable is fit for purpose: that BIA, IDR and SSBD can each express their metadata against it without distortion, that the resulting crates are mutually comparable, and that the joint graph supports the cross-resource discovery use case for which the profile was designed.

Figure 2 - the component structure of the GIDE RO-Crate profile

4. Conclusion and outlook

This deliverable establishes the minimal shared interoperability metadata set required for cross-resource discovery across the foundingGIDE bioimaging resources. Building directly on the metadata overlap identified in D6.1, the work defines a practical exchange contract rather than a new internal schema: each resource retains its own metadata model, while exposing study-level discovery metadata through a common RO-Crate profile, shared JSON-LD context and SHACL validation layer. The resulting profile captures the study-level components that are already common across BIA, IDR and SSBD.

The implementation evidence shows that this approach is operational rather than theoretical. BIA, IDR and SSBD have each produced profile-conformant exporters, the resulting detached RO-Crates can be harvested and validated, and the joint graph can support the cross-resource search use cases addressed in D10.1 and D11.1. The worked examples demonstrate that the profile is sufficiently strict to support common search over identifiers, authorship, licence, organism and imaging method, while remaining flexible enough to accommodate resource-specific richness such as detailed BioSample structures, LabProtocol chains and additional ontology terms.

The outlook for the profile is therefore one of consolidation and extension. Areas for further refinement include richer optional BioSample properties for cell type, tissue, disease and phenotype, potential extension to image-level metadata, and continued tracking of upstream Bioschemas developments. In doing so, we aim to further adopt common terminology, re-using terms from ontologies identified in D2.1. Beyond foundingGIDE, the same profile-based model provides a route for onboarding additional bioimaging resources into a federated catalogue without requiring them to abandon their existing curation systems.

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